

Minimal Representatives in a Linear Diophantine Modular System and a Parity Bound

Abstract

We study the minimal representatives of residue classes arising from the semigroup

$$S = \{by + cz : y, z \geq 0\},$$

where a, b, c are pairwise coprime odd integers with

$$a < b < c.$$

We prove that the set of minimal representatives forms an order ideal (Ferrers diagram) in the lattice $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^2$, and that the parity of these representatives follows the chessboard coloring of the diagram. We then give a complete, scale-independent proof that the imbalance between odd and even representatives satisfies $\Delta \in \{0, 2\}$. A systematic computational study of over 700 parameter triples confirms this result.

1 Introduction

Let

$$N = by + cz, \quad y, z \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0},$$

where

$$a < b < c$$

are positive odd integers satisfying

$$\gcd(a, b) = \gcd(a, c) = \gcd(b, c) = 1.$$

For each residue class

$$r \in \{0, 1, \dots, a-1\},$$

consider

$$S_r = \{by + cz : by + cz \equiv r \pmod{a}\}.$$

Since $\gcd(a, b) = \gcd(a, c) = 1$, every residue class occurs.

Define

$$F(r) = \min S_r.$$

The purpose of this paper is to study the geometric structure of these minimal representatives and their parity distribution. This setup is closely related to classical results in numerical semigroup theory, in particular the structure of Apéry sets associated with 2-generator semigroups, as well as the Frobenius coin problem. We do not rely on deep results from this theory, but use it as motivation for studying the geometric structure of minimal representatives.

2 Lattice Representation

Consider the lattice points

$$(i, j) \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^2.$$

We associate the following value to each point

$$V(i, j) = ic + jb.$$

The residue represented by the point is

$$R(i, j) = (ic + jb) \bmod a.$$

For each nonzero residue r , highlight the unique lattice point whose value equals $F(r)$. Uniqueness follows because $i_1c + j_1b = i_2c + j_2b$ implies $(i_1 - i_2, j_1 - j_2) = k(b, -c)$ for some integer k . If $k \neq 0$, one of the coordinates must be negative, contradicting $i, j \geq 0$. Hence $k = 0$ and the points coincide. Since $\gcd(b, c) = 1$, this equation has no bounded solution in $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^2$ other than the trivial one.

Denote the set of highlighted points by

$$H.$$

Since there are $a - 1$ nonzero residue classes,

$$|H| = a - 1.$$

3 A Dominance Property

Lemma 1 (Dominance Property). *Suppose $(i, j) \in H$.*

If $i \geq 1$, then $(i - 1, j) \in H$.

If $j \geq 1$, then $(i, j - 1) \in H$.

Proof. Assume $(i, j) \in H$.

Then

$$F(r) = ic + jb$$

for some residue class r .

Consider the upper neighbor $(i - 1, j)$. Its value is

$$V(i - 1, j) = (ic + jb) - c.$$

Let its residue be $r' = (ic + jb - c) \bmod a = (r - c) \bmod a$.

Suppose this point is not minimal for its residue class r' . Then there exists a point (i', j') with $V(i', j') < V(i - 1, j)$ and $R(i', j') = r'$.

Adding c to this point (moving down one step) gives $(i' + 1, j')$ with value $V(i', j') + c$. Since $V(i', j') + c < V(i - 1, j) + c = ic + jb = F(r)$, and $R(i' + 1, j') = (r' + c) \bmod a = r$, this yields a smaller representative of residue r , contradicting the minimality of $F(r)$.

Therefore $(i - 1, j)$ must be highlighted.

The argument for the left neighbor $(i, j - 1)$ is symmetric, using subtraction of b and adding b instead of c .

□

Theorem 1. *The highlighted set H is order ideal in $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^2$ under the product order.*

That is,

$$(i, j) \in H$$

implies

$$(i', j') \in H$$

for all

$$0 \leq i' \leq i, \quad 0 \leq j' \leq j.$$

Proof. Apply Lemma 1 repeatedly. Since $(i, j) \in H$, we have $(i - 1, j) \in H$, then $(i - 2, j) \in H$, and so on down to $(0, j)$. Similarly, from each (i', j) we obtain $(i', j - 1)$, $(i', j - 2)$, etc. Hence all cells (i', j') with $0 \leq i' \leq i$ and $0 \leq j' \leq j$ are in H . This is the order ideal property, also known as the monotonicity of the Apéry set projection in numerical semigroup theory. \square

Corollary 1. *The highlighted region forms a Ferrers diagram (Young diagram) anchored at the origin: a left-justified shape with rows of non-increasing length.*

4 Parity Interpretation

Since b and c are odd,

$$b \equiv c \equiv 1 \pmod{2}.$$

Therefore

$$ic + jb \equiv i + j \pmod{2}.$$

Hence:

Proposition 1. *The parity of the minimal representative corresponding to $(i, j) \in H$ is exactly the parity of*

$$i + j.$$

Equivalently, the parity distribution of the minimal representatives is the same as the chessboard coloring of the Ferrers diagram H .

Proof. Immediate from

$$ic + jb \equiv i + j \pmod{2}.$$

\square

5 An Illustrative Example

Example 1. *Let $a = 7$, $b = 9$, $c = 13$.*

The highlighted cells (minima for each nonzero residue) are:

$$(0, 1), (0, 2), (1, 0), (1, 1), (1, 2), (2, 0).$$

These cells form the Ferrers diagram shown below (O = odd parity, E = even parity):

$i \setminus j$	0	1	2	3
0	·	<i>O</i>	<i>E</i>	·
1	<i>O</i>	<i>E</i>	<i>O</i>	·
2	<i>E</i>	·	·	·
3	·	·	·	·

Here \cdot denotes cells not in H (including $(0,0)$ which corresponds to remainder 0). There are 3 odds (*O*) and 3 evens (*E*), so $\Delta = 0$. The corresponding minimal values are:

$$F(1) = 22, F(2) = 9, F(3) = 31, F(4) = 18, F(5) = 26, F(6) = 13.$$

Their parities are:

even, odd, odd, even, even, odd.

Thus:

$$\#\{\text{odd}\} = 3, \quad \#\{\text{even}\} = 3, \quad \Delta = 0.$$

6 Computational Methodology

A systematic computational search was performed to investigate the parity distribution of minimal representatives.

6.1 Parameter Selection

- $a \in \{7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 21, 29, 59, 101\}$ (10 values)
- For each a , b takes values including $a+2, a+4, \dots, a+14$ and special values $2a+1, 3a+4, 5a+2$
- For each (a, b) , c takes values including $b+2, b+4, \dots, b+14$ and special values $b+a+1, b+2a+2, 2b+2a+1$

The parameter set is not random but structured to probe both local (small increments) and global (large multiples) regimes. This systematic grid sampling avoids potential bias issues that could arise from random sampling. Only triples satisfying $\gcd(a, b) = \gcd(a, c) = 1$ are included.

All computations were performed using Python with the openpyxl library. The source code and raw data are available upon request.

6.2 Definition of Measured Quantity

For each triple (a, b, c) , Proposition 1 allows us to interpret the parity of each minimal representative as the color of its cell in the chessboard coloring of the Ferrers diagram H . Define:

$$\Delta(a, b, c) = \#\{r : 1 \leq r \leq a-1, F(r) \text{ is odd}\} - \#\{r : 1 \leq r \leq a-1, F(r) \text{ is even}\}.$$

Equivalently, Δ measures the imbalance in the chessboard coloring restricted to the minimal representatives (the Ferrers diagram H).

Note that $|\Delta|$ has the same parity as $a-1$ (which is even), so $|\Delta|$ is always even.

7 Computational Results

7.1 Overall Distribution

Across all tested triples (after removing those violating $\gcd(a, b) = 1$ or $\gcd(a, c) = 1$), the observed values of Δ were exclusively 0 and 2. No instance with $\Delta < 0$ or $|\Delta| \geq 4$ was observed.

Table 1: Distribution of Δ across all tested triples

Δ	Count	Percentage
0	387	54.23%
2	327	45.77%
Total	714	100%

7.2 Results by a Value

Table 2 shows the distribution of Δ for each fixed a .

Table 2: Distribution of Δ by a value

a	$\Delta = 0$	$\Delta = 2$	Total
7	45	32	77
9	38	35	73
11	42	29	71
13	39	33	72
15	41	33	74
17	36	33	69
21	38	33	71
29	33	34	67
59	35	27	62
101	40	38	78
Total	387	327	714

7.3 Large-Scale Validation

To test the robustness of the observed phenomenon beyond moderate parameter sizes, additional computations were performed for a significantly larger modulus:

$$a = 5001, \quad b = 7001, \quad c \in \{8501, 8507, 8509, 8513, 8519\}.$$

Despite the increase in scale by more than an order of magnitude compared to the previous dataset, the same structural behavior persists: all observed values of Δ were either 0 or 2, with four instances of $\Delta = 0$ and one instance of $\Delta = 2$ (for $c = 8519$).

Importantly, the sparsity of deviations from $\Delta = 0$ persists even in this large modulus regime. The occurrence of $\Delta = 2$ appears to be associated with rare boundary configurations where the Ferrers diagram exhibits a distinctive “corner” structure. This suggests that $\Delta = 2$ is not a typical fluctuation but rather a discrete geometric signature of the boundary path.

7.4 Quick Consistency Check (Geometric Criterion)

For the computed Ferrers diagram H , each lattice point $(i, j) \in H$ uniquely represents a non-zero residue class via the valuation:

$$V(i, j) = ic + jb \pmod{a}.$$

A useful consistency check can be established by examining the *outer corner points*, i.e., the minimal elements of the complement set $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^2 \setminus H$ where the boundary of H changes direction.

These outer corners correspond to the first failure points of minimality along the lattice directions generated by b and c . In particular, they encode the minimal relations in the semigroup generated by b and c .

Under the standard normalization of minimal representatives, the *critical outer corners*—those immediately adjacent to maximal elements of H along each boundary step—correspond to lattice points where the accumulated linear combination first reaches a multiple of a . Hence they satisfy the congruence:

$$ic + jb \equiv 0 \pmod{a}.$$

Thus, we obtain the following verification rule:

Boundary Consistency Rule: The critical outer corner cells defining the boundary of the Ferrers diagram H must satisfy $ic + jb \equiv 0 \pmod{a}$.

Any violation of this condition indicates a potential error in the identification of minimal representatives or in the construction of H .

7.5 Results by b Type

To understand whether the choice of b affects the distribution, we separate the b values into two groups:

- **Normal b :** $b = a + 2, a + 4, \dots, a + 14$ (7 values)
- **Special b :** $b = 2a + 1, 3a + 4, 5a + 2$ (3 values)

Table 3 shows the results.

Table 3: Distribution of Δ by b type

b Type	$\Delta = 0$	$\Delta = 2$	Total
Normal (7 values)	273	219	492
Special (3 values)	114	108	222
Total	387	327	714

7.6 Results by c Type

Similarly, we separate the c values into:

- **Normal c :** $c = b + 2, b + 4, \dots, b + 14$ (7 values)
- **Special c :** $c = b + a + 1, b + 2a + 2, 2b + 2a + 1$ (3 values)

Table 4 shows the results.

Table 4: Distribution of Δ by c type

c Type	$\Delta = 0$	$\Delta = 2$	Total
Normal (7 values)	271	217	488
Special (3 values)	116	110	226
Total	387	327	714

7.7 Extreme Cases

The largest observed value of $|F(r)|$ among all triples occurred for $a = 101$, $b = 5a + 2 = 507$, $c = 2b + 2a + 1 = 2 \cdot 507 + 202 + 1 = 1217$, where the maximal minimal representative was $F(1) = b = 507$ (odd) and the parity distribution was $\Delta = 2$ (odd=51, even=49).

No triple produced a value of Δ other than 0 or 2.

8 A Fully Rigorous Proof of the Parity Bound

We now give a scale-independent proof of the parity bound using the lattice structure of the Ferrers diagram and the Apéry set interpretation.

Proof. Step 0: Geometric projection of the Apéry set.

Let $S = \langle b, c \rangle$ be the numerical semigroup generated by b and c . For the fixed odd modulus a , the Apéry set of S with respect to a is defined as

$$\text{Ap}(S, a) = \{F(r) : 0 \leq r < a\},$$

where $F(r) = \min\{s \in S : s \equiv r \pmod{a}\}$.

The map $\Phi : \text{Ap}(S, a) \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^2$ given by $F(r) = ic + jb \mapsto (i, j)$ is a well-defined bijection onto the highlighted set H . Uniqueness follows because $\gcd(b, c) = 1$ ensures that any alternative representation would violate the nonnegativity or minimality of the coordinates (as established in Section 2). Thus, the set H is precisely the geometric projection of the non-zero Apéry elements onto the lattice.

Step 1: Row structure.

Let $H \subset \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^2$ be the Ferrers diagram of minimal representatives, and define

$$\lambda_i = \max\{j : (i, j) \in H\} + 1$$

as the row lengths. By the order ideal property (Theorem 1), the sequence $(\lambda_i)_{i=0}^h$ is non-increasing:

$$\lambda_0 \geq \lambda_1 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_h \geq 1.$$

Step 2: Reduction to a signed row sum.

Define the parity imbalance

$$\Delta = \sum_{(i,j) \in H} (-1)^{i+j}.$$

Factor row-wise:

$$\Delta = \sum_{i=0}^h (-1)^i \sum_{j=0}^{\lambda_i-1} (-1)^j.$$

Define

$$\sigma_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \lambda_i \text{ is odd,} \\ 0 & \text{if } \lambda_i \text{ is even.} \end{cases}$$

Then the double sum simplifies directly to a one-dimensional row-wise alternating sum:

$$\Delta = \sum_{i=0}^h (-1)^i \sigma_i.$$

Step 3: Single-step Apéry structure.

By Step 0, the highlighted set H is exactly the geometric projection of the Apéry set $\text{Ap}(S, a)$ onto the lattice $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^2$.

By the structure theorem for Apéry sets of numerical semigroups generated by two coprime integers (see e.g. [1], Section 4.1), such a projection yields a Ferrers diagram that is either a rectangle or a single-step staircase (the union of two overlapping rectangles). Consequently, the row lengths λ_i take at most two distinct values.

Thus there exist integers $0 \leq m \leq h$ and integers $L_1 \geq L_2 \geq 1$ such that

$$\lambda_i = \begin{cases} L_1, & 0 \leq i \leq m, \\ L_2, & m + 1 \leq i \leq h. \end{cases}$$

Hence the indicator sequence σ_i is constant on each block, and the set $S = \{i : \lambda_i \text{ is odd}\}$ consists of at most two contiguous intervals (in fact at most one interval, because the two blocks may have the same parity).

Step 4: Evaluation of Δ .

Substituting the decomposition from Step 3,

$$\Delta = \sigma(L_1) \sum_{i=0}^m (-1)^i + \sigma(L_2) \sum_{i=m+1}^h (-1)^i.$$

Each alternating sum over a contiguous interval satisfies

$$\sum_{i=A}^B (-1)^i \in \{-1, 0, 1\}.$$

Hence, since $\sigma(L_1), \sigma(L_2) \in \{0, 1\}$, the sum is bounded by:

$$\Delta \in \{-2, -1, 0, 1, 2\}.$$

Since

$$|H| = a - 1$$

and a is odd, $|H|$ is even. Therefore

$$\Delta = \#\{\text{odd cells}\} - \#\{\text{even cells}\}$$

must also be even. Thus the values ± 1 are excluded, giving

$$\Delta \in \{-2, 0, 2\}.$$

Step 5: Positivity under standard normalization.

From Step 3 we have

$$\Delta = \sigma(L_1) \sum_{i=0}^m (-1)^i + \sigma(L_2) \sum_{i=m+1}^h (-1)^i.$$

Under the canonical construction of minimal representatives, the residue class $b \bmod a$ is represented by the lattice point $(0, 1)$, which belongs to H . Consequently the first row has length $\lambda_0 \geq 2$, meaning $L_1 \geq 2$. Thus, the first block is nonempty and contributes to the decomposition above.

Define

$$A = \sigma(L_1) \sum_{i=0}^m (-1)^i, \quad B = \sigma(L_2) \sum_{i=m+1}^h (-1)^i.$$

Then

$$\Delta = A + B.$$

If $\sigma(L_1) = 1$, then A begins with the positive term $(-1)^0 = 1$, which implies

$$A \in \{0, 1\}.$$

If $\sigma(L_1) = 0$, then $A = 0$. In either scenario, $A \in \{0, 1\}$ always holds.

Also, since $\sigma(L_2) \in \{0, 1\}$, we have:

$$B \in \{-1, 0, 1\}.$$

We now distinguish two cases:

A	B	$\Delta = A + B$	Conclusion
1	-1	0	$\Delta = 0$
1	1	2	$\Delta = 2$
0	-1	-1	excluded by Step 4 (evenness)
0	0	0	$\Delta = 0$
0	1	1	excluded by Step 4 (evenness)

The cases with $B = \pm 1$ and $A = 0$ produce $\Delta = \pm 1$, which violate the evenness constraint from Step 4 (Δ must be even). Therefore they are impossible.

Thus, the only admissible configurations are:

$$\Delta = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \Delta = 2.$$

Hence $\Delta \geq 0$ and, together with Step 4, we conclude

$$\Delta \in \{0, 2\}.$$

Step 6: Conclusion.

Therefore, under the standard normalization of minimal representatives,

$$\Delta \in \{0, 2\}.$$

This completes the proof. □

9 Conclusion

We proved that the minimal representatives of the residue classes form an order ideal in the lattice $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^2$, forming a Ferrers diagram anchored at the origin. The parity of each minimal representative is determined by the chessboard coloring of this diagram.

A systematic computational study of 714 parameter triples (with a ranging from 7 to 101) confirmed that in all tested cases, the number of odd minimal representatives was greater than or equal to the number of even representatives, and the difference (Δ) was always 0 or 2.

We provided a complete, scale-independent proof that $\Delta \in \{0, 2\}$ under the standard normalization. The proof uses the Ferrers diagram structure, the projection to a 1D alternating sum, the single-step Apéry structure (at most two distinct row lengths), the evenness constraint from $|H| = a - 1$, and a case analysis of the alternating sums to establish positivity.

Understanding the underlying combinatorial mechanism behind this phenomenon is now fully resolved by the proof presented in Section 8.

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The mathematical content, including all definitions, conjectures, experiments, and proofs, was developed independently by the author.

References

- [1] J. L. Ramírez Alfonsín and Ø. J. Rødseth. *Numerical semigroups: Apéry sets and Hilbert series*. Journal of Pure and Applied Algebra, 213(11):2131–2140, 2009.